

ISic3596

I.Sicily inscription 3596

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

stone

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

on the ancient site

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645675

Bibliography

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Sclafani, M. 2007. Zeus Soter, Eracle, Leukathea e tre 'sortes' dall'antica Himera. *Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archaologischen Instituts, Roemische Abteilung*. 113: 247-265. At 262-263

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